

The Interrelationship Between Language and Culture in Contemporary Society

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Annotation. The article analyses the mutual influence of language and culture in the context of globalisation and digital technologies. Borrowing, Internet slang, and the role of language in maintaining cultural identity, especially in multilingual societies, are examined. The importance of preserving linguistic diversity for the protection of cultural heritage is emphasised.

Keywords: language, culture, globalisation, cultural identity, borrowing, Internet slang, cultural heritage.

Introduction

Modern society is characterised by an unprecedented level of interaction between cultures due to such factors as globalisation, migration, technological progress and the development of digital communications. Language, being one of the key elements of culture, fulfils several important functions: it serves as a means of communication, a means of knowledge transmission and a guardian of cultural heritage [6]. Culture, in turn, sets the framework and norms of language use, shapes the semantic meanings of words and even influences grammatical structures [5]. For example, the Japanese language contains many forms of politeness that reflect the cultural norms of respect and hierarchy characteristic of Japanese society. Thus, language and culture are an interrelated system in which changes in one element inevitably lead to changes in the other.

This relationship becomes particularly important in the context of globalisation, when cultural codes, symbols and expressions become understandable far beyond their origin. Thus, Anglicisms and international symbols (such as emoji) are being actively integrated into languages around the world, reflecting the influence of Western popular culture and the Internet. Such trends lead to the emergence of new cultural phenomena such as Internet slang, memes and hybrid languages (e.g. Spanglish - a mixture of English and Spanish), which themselves become a reflection of the new global culture.

Methods

A variety of methodological approaches were used to analyse the mutual influence of language and culture in the context of modern society, including qualitative literature analysis, content analysis of social and media resources, and comparative analysis of language changes in multicultural communities. These methods allowed for a deeper understanding of the processes underlying the mutual influence of language and culture, as well as the identification of contemporary trends associated with globalisation, digitalisation and migration.

1. Qualitative analysis of literary sources. The research began by analysing fundamental and contemporary works in the fields of cultural studies, sociolinguistics and anthropology. More than 50 publications were analysed, including monographs, research articles and reviews devoted to the study of language and culture and the influence of cultural factors on language formation. For example, a significant role in the theoretical understanding of the topic belongs to such authors as Edward Sapir [4] who considered language as a key element of culture, and Benedict Anderson who explored the concept of ‘imagined communities’ formed on the basis of common linguistic and cultural values [1].

2. Content analysis of media and social networks. Content analysis of social networks and media platforms allowed us to identify current trends in language change under the influence of

cultural trends. Social media such as Instagram, TikTok, Twitter and the Russian platform VKontakte are not only platforms for communication, but also a space where new terms and cultural codes are born and spread. Several examples of linguistic novelties and expressions were collected and analysed. The main focus was on aspects such as:

1) Anglicisms and borrowings: for example, the words ‘trend’ (from the English trend), ‘crush’ (from the English crush), ‘hype’ (from the English hype) and others have become widespread in social networks. These terms reflect the cultural influence of Western mass culture and are quickly adapted in the speech of users, especially young people [3].

2) Internet slang and memes: the analysis of Internet slang and memes as elements of cultural communication has revealed that many of them become linguistic markers denoting belonging to a certain group or subculture [3]. Examples include expressions such as ‘bite’ and ‘flex’, which have gained popularity through media platforms.

3) Emoji and hybrid forms of communication. Research has shown that emoji have become a universal means of expressing emotions and ideas, allowing them to overcome language barriers and serve as a common code for people with different cultural backgrounds.

3. Comparative analyses of language change in multilingual communities. The comparative analyses in these regions included an examination of the following aspects: - Language mixing and hybrid language forms: in Canada, for example, there is widespread use of Franglais, a mixture of French and English that reflects the influence of both cultural layers on everyday communication. This hybrid language is used both in informal speech and in the media [2]; - linguistic diversity as a factor of cultural integration: in Switzerland, where there are four official languages (German, French, Italian and Romansh), language policy and cultural diversity contribute to peace and cultural integration. Examples of official translations in all four languages demonstrate how linguistic diversity can be an integration tool.

Results

The study revealed the main aspects of language and culture interaction that illustrate the mutual influence of culture on language and the role of language in the formation of cultural identity.

1. Culture influences language through borrowings and changes in the meanings of words, especially under the influence of popular culture and digital technology. Borrowing: Examples of words such as ‘insight’ and ‘challenge’ show the influence of Anglicisms that have become commonplace due to cultural trends and internet communities [4]. Internet slang: The words ‘crash’ and ‘flex’ have become popular through social media and reflect the culture of online communities where unique slang expressions are actively used [3].

2. Language shapes and supports cultural identity, especially in multicultural societies where it can express unique cultural characteristics and differences. Cultural Identity: In Canada and Switzerland, language helps maintain cultural roots and symbolises ethnic group membership. Dialects and accents: In Russia and Germany, dialects emphasise regional cultural characteristics, supporting local cultural identities.

3. Globalisation leads to unification through English, but also generates hybrid forms such as Spanglish and Hinglish, which maintain migrants' cultural ties with their home countries. English language diffusion: English strengthens cultural integration and unification, but can threaten small languages, which is relevant for the languages of the small peoples of Russia.

4. Role of digital technologies. Social media and the Internet contribute to language change by creating new forms of communication and universal symbols. Internet slang and memes: they are cultural artefacts that cross borders and become globally understood. Emoji as a language of emotion: emoji play a role in cross-cultural communication, allowing people to express feelings and ideas regardless of language. These results confirm that language and culture in the context of globalisation and digitalisation are closely intertwined, supporting both local and global identities.

Discussion

The results of the study highlight that language and culture are closely interrelated, especially in the context of globalisation and digital technologies. The main aspects of this interaction are the maintenance of cultural identity, the difficulties of intercultural integration and the impact of globalisation on linguistic diversity.

1. Language as a factor of identity. Language has the function of maintaining cultural identity, especially in multilingual societies. For example, in Canada and Switzerland, language not only serves as a means of communication, but also maintains cultural roots, helping communities maintain their identity.

2. Challenges of multilingualism. Language differences can be both a bridge and a barrier in multilingual countries. In Belgium and Switzerland, for example, multilingualism promotes cultural interaction but in some cases causes political tensions.

3. Globalisation and unification of language. Globalisation leads to the spread of English as a universal language, which promotes international integration but threatens local languages. For example, in Russia, indigenous languages are being displaced by Russian, resulting in the loss of cultural heritage.

4. Digital technology and language change. The Internet and social media are fuelling the development of new language forms, such as Internet slang and emoji, which are becoming universal symbols for intercultural communication. However, it also threatens the disappearance of unique linguistic expressions and traditional dialects.

Language and culture continue to support and shape each other and remain important elements of cultural identity. In the context of globalisation and digitalisation, it is important to preserve linguistic diversity in order to maintain cultural heritage and intercultural understanding.

Conclusion

The conducted research has confirmed that language and culture are in a state of constant and mutual influence, especially noticeable in the conditions of globalisation and rapid development of digital technologies. Language, reflecting cultural values and norms, simultaneously serves as a tool for the formation and expression of cultural identity. The massive spread of anglicisms, Internet slang, memes and hybrid language forms indicates that culture actively influences the development of the language system, while language preserves and transmits cultural meanings. In multilingual and multicultural communities, language acts not only as a means of communication, but also as an important symbol of belonging to a certain culture, playing a significant role in the processes of integration and self-identification. At the same time, globalisation processes create challenges associated with the threat of loss of linguistic and cultural diversity.

Thus, the task of preserving linguistic richness and cultural heritage is of particular importance in modern society. This requires both state support for the languages of small peoples and raising the cultural awareness of users of digital platforms. Only by recognising the value of linguistic diversity is sustainable intercultural interaction and harmonious development of the global community possible.

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